

EXPLANATION OF ETHNOCULTURAL TOPICS IN THE THEATRE OF YOUNG SPECTATORS

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Summary

The thesis deals with the theatre's tour of the districts, which actors played which roles. "The team of the children's theater of the Republic (37 people) was sent on a tour of all districts by the Directorate for art affairs, next to the USSR Sovnarkom, in order to provide cultural services to the children of the Republic during the summer holiday season. The theater's repertoire plan consists of the plays "Oysha", "engineer child" and "one family", and one more excellent concert program. The tour will be held in Pioneer camps, large squares, schools in all districts for more than two months, providing cultural services to children on art," the newspaper reported.

Key words

theatre, repertoire , performance, culture, formation.

The Karakalpak State theatre for young spectators was founded in 1978. This is not the first theatre organisation in Karakalpakstan. In 1930, together with the Karakalpak State Theatre, the Russian theatre and children's theatre began their creative activities. Theatrical art is evidence of great importance for our people in their spiritual upbringing.

Articles were published about the theatre's tour of the districts, which actors played which roles. "The team of the children's theatre of the Republic (37 people) was sent on a tour of all districts by the Directorate for art affairs, next to the USSR Sovnarkom, in order to provide cultural services to the children of the Republic during the summer holiday season. The theatre's repertoire plan consists of the plays "Oysha", "engineer child" and "one family", and one more excellent concert program. The tour will be held in Pioneer camps, large squares, schools in all districts for more than two months, providing cultural services to children on art," the newspaper reported.

It can be seen that the children's theatre of the Republic has several performances from its current repertoire. Despite the fact that the directors of these performances are unknown, they were certainly plays on the topic of youth. The theater also had several staff members on the staff schedule. Proof of this is the fact that he went on tour as part of 37 employees. In addition to performances, he has also presented concert programs for children. The above-mentioned play "Oysha", the theater repertoire of which has become more rich

with the works of National Playwrights, belongs to the pen of the people's writer of Karakalpakstan, laureate of the State prize named after Berdakh, Sapar Khojaniyazov.

Starting in 1936, when he entered the Lunacharsky Institute of theatre arts in Moscow, the Karakalpak studio, S.Khozhanियazov's life will be deeply connected with theatrical art.

S.Khojaniyazov graduated from the theatre institute in 1939 and, as a qualified cadre, begins to actively interfere in the cultural construction of our Republic, especially in the life of theatre, art, performing acting, directing, playwright duties. S.Khojaniyazov was marked as a playwright in the history of Karakalpak literature. His "Oysha" (1940), "Biziñ bahadir" (1944), "Syymegege suykenbe" (1945), "Ziyada" (1946), "Jas jyrekler" (1953), "Bakhit" (1957), "talo'as" (1962), "Arios" (1964), "Aqmaq patsha" (1968), "Maman biy" his plays such as (1971) have been one of the current repertoires in Karakalpak state theatre and young audience theatres for many years.

S.Khozhanियazov entered playwriting with the musical drama "Oysha", written in 1938-1939. The play, which won first place in the 1940 competition for Best dramatic work, was first performed at the Republican children's theatre in 1941". In the play "Oysha", events related to the marriage of the Karakalpak people of the early 20th century are written.

The work is in the genre of tragedy, which reveals the bitter reality of Oysha's miserable life, a victim of injustice, with Aytjan, who sought truth, equality, free love in feudal times. The plot of the play begins with the story of the fall in the Ram of the rich, Seybil and Uzaqbergan. Seybil, a World-War II Seybil who, not counting women as human beings, is surrounded by feudal era glimpses that count her as a mole, becomes interested in the mole and even tries to sell her daughter, Oysha, to a rich man called Uzaqbergan, for a thick mole.

In the case of Oysha, the young man who worked at his father's door, his own equal, Aytjan, had a crush. On the day the wedding is marked and transmitted, Oysha is determined to run away with Aytjan. They are called this "journey of love" by Bektursin, the peasant of Seybil boy, the Oyzadas will work hard to help. However, as the young people who truly love each other escape, they are caught by the riverbank. Finally, the Oysha is forcibly transferred to Uzaqbergan. Aytjan, who wants to save Oysha, is shot and killed by Uzaqbergan. Unable to bear this, Oysha also escapes Uzaqbergan's House and is forced to commit suicide at the beginning of Aytjan's grave. This play, which shows the

heavy past marriage of the Karakalpak people, serves as a upbringing not only for young people, but also for adults.

In addition to the children's theatre, he carried out many educational work on a Republican scale, the skill of actors and actresses began to grow and become known to the people.

Our famous artists, The Late people's artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan Orazgul Davletova, honored in Uzbekistan, people's artist of Karakalpakstan Orazbay Umitkulovs cites their labor activities as acting as an actress in the theatre of children, young spectators of the Republic in the city of Fourkul. From 1943 he continued his creative career at the Karakalpak state musical theatre, now named after Berdakh.

The main law of the theatre is the confrontation of the audience taking place in Sakhna, interesting with its inner world. The culture of the audience is mainly attached to the performance presented to the viewer. Performances should be liberalized depending on the age of the audience. For children:

By the 1970s and 1980s, the art of Karakalpak theatre would become much more recognizable to the former All-Union republics. The theatre employs qualified specialists, its current repertoire is enriched by performances of various educational importance. National playwriting thrives, world dramaturgy patterns are staged and referenced to audiences. In the upbringing of young people, it began to be known that the importance of Performing Arts is great in the proper organization of their free time, in directing them to creativity, in the formation of their culture and the introduction of other positive sensations. Taking into account these, a youth theatre was necessary in Karakalpakstan.

On the basis of the Decree No. 173 of the Republican government of March 22, 1978, from September 1 of this year, it was necessary to start its work at the Republican theatre of young spectators in the city of Nukus, the center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Taking into account the organizational, creative and material difficulties of the newly established theater, the leadership of the Republic laid the foundation for the kidney of the Ministry of culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan dated March 30, 1978, the role of director of the new theater, many years of experience in organizational and creative work, people's artist of the republics of Uzbekistan, Karakalpakstan and Tatarstan, the head director of the theatre is the actor and director of the Karakalpak state musical drama and comedy theatre, people's artist of Uzbekistan Najimatdin Ansatbayev.

As well as laying the foundation for the theatre, this highly experienced trio had also defined a creative tradition and a new trend.

Theatre actors were also encouraged by the contemporary K.S.The Karakalpak named after Stanislavsky receives from the actors of the state musical drama and comedy theatre. All graduates of the acting department of the Tashkent state institute of theatre and painting from 1976 to 1977 are admitted to the theatre of young spectators with fullness

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